

PASSAGE OF THE PERIOD OF REST IN POTATO STORAGE

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One of the main biological properties of potatoes that ensure their durability is their physiological rest period. All measures in the storage of potatoes should be aimed at extending the dormancy period.

The durability of potatoes depends on the content of substances other than natural protection - solanine and chakanin glucosides, polyphenols.

Depending on the speed of the processes that take place in potatoes during storage, its storage can be divided into three periods.

The first period is the post-harvest or treatment period. During this period, synthetic processes prevail over hydrolytic processes, and the amount of substances such as starch and protein increases in the bud. These processes slow down the vital activity of the fetus and prepare it for the transition to the dormant period. In addition, during this period, a scar tissue is formed in the cut and injured places. The fabric protects against damage by nodular microorganisms and water evaporation from it. During the treatment period, the temperature of the air should be 15-18°C, the humidity should be 85-95 percent, and the warehouse should be ventilated.

Potatoes will not last long if they are well ripe and not damaged during digging. On the other hand, the treatment period for immature and damaged potatoes will be prolonged.

The second period comes after the cooling treatment period. A characteristic feature of this period is that the air temperature drops to 4-5°C. In this case, the dormant period and other processes of the tumor slow down.

During the transition from the treatment period to the cooling period, the air temperature is reduced by 1-0.5°C per day to 4-5°C. This period is continued for 20-40 days.

The third period corresponds to winter and spring, this time is called the main period. During this period, potato tubers go through a period of physiological rest, and then a period of forced rest begins. During this period, low air temperature prevents potatoes from growing.

In our conditions, buds turn blue in spring and summer. The results of our experiment showed that the death rate of potatoes due to browning was 4% in winter, and 2-3% in summer.

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